

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP for EI source maintenance for GC Q – Exactive

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Author: Kateřina Coufalíková

Summary

This section describes EI Source maintenance, removing ion source cartridge form GC Q – Exactive, cleaning procedure for EI source components (Ion Cartridge Sleeve, Lens 3/RF Lens, Lens 2, Lens 1, Ion Volume, Repeller, Ion Volume – Repeller Insulator, Repeller, Ion Volume – Repeller Insulator, Repeller Nut, Repeller Spring, Ion Volume Locking Ring).

IMPORTANT

- Always place the components on a clean, lint-free surface (aluminum foil)
- Use a new pair of lint- and powder free gloves before starting each removal and cleaning
- Make sure that you do not introduce any scratches or surface abrasion by using inappropriate tools
- Cooled down EI ion source before maintenance. Be careful, the ion source can reach temperatures up to 350°C. Wait until the ion source has cooled down to room temperature before you begin working on it.
- Never use for source cleaning chloroform (may damage the Ion Source Cartridge)
- Never use dichlormethane for cleaning plastic/ceramic parts of the source.
- Ion Volume-Repeller Insulator clean only in high temperature oven (cleaning typically not needed). The use of solvents and a sonicator can destroy the porous ceramic material)

To remove the Ion Source Cartridge from GC Q - Exactive

For removing Ion Source Cartridge from through vacuum interlock is used Source Exchange Tool (see Figure 1). This procedure is used to maintain a good vacuum level in the

instrument. The whole procedure is recorded on video "Remove cartridge" and "Install cartridge"

Figure 1. Source Exchange Tool (for remove and insert the Ion Source Cartridge through the vacuum interlock)

1. Cool down ion source interface. Set Transfer line temp and Ion source temp to 25 °C and wait until the ion source has cooled down to room temperature (~ 60 minutes)
2. Put the GC Q - Exactive to off mode
3. Unfold and slide down the Vacuum Interlock Handle see Figure 2.
4. Remove the Vacuum Interlock Plug (by rotating)
5. Connect the Source Exchange Tool (by rotating)
6. Press the **Evacuate** button (to remove any air inside the vacuum interlock) and wait until is green "Ready to Open"
7. Lift up the Vacuum Interlock Handle
8. Slide the Source Exchange Tool to the instrument on the right track, then rotate to left and pull back the Source Exchange tool from instrument
9. Lower the vacuum interlock handle

10. Rotate and remove the Source Exchange Tool from the instrument (inside the Source Exchange Tool should be Ion Source Cartridge)
11. Put back the Vacuum Interlock Plug (by rotating)
12. Collapse the Vacuum Interlock Handle back to starting position
13. The removed Ion Source Cartridge should be inside the Source Exchange Tool (it is necessary to remove it using Removing Ion Source Cartridge see Figure 3.). Be careful, the ion source cartridge is very hot, let the ion source cartridge cool before working on it.

Figure 2. Evacuating the system

Figure 3. Removing Ion Source Cartridge

To install Ion Source Cartridge to GC Q - Exactive

Before inserting the Ion Source Cartridge to the Source Exchange Tool make sure that it is properly assembled

1. Insert the Ion Source Cardridge to the Source Exchange Tool (the Ion Source Cartridge should be fully covered with Source Exchange Tool)
2. Unfold the Vacuum Interlock Handle
3. Remove the Vacuum Interlock Plug (by rotating)
4. Connect the Source Exchange Tool (by rotating)
5. Press the **Evacuate** button and wait until "Ready to open" light to turn green
6. Lift up on the Vacuum Interlock Handle
7. Slide the Source Exchange Tool into the instrument on the left track, rotate to the right and then pull back to the starting position
8. Lower the Vacuum Interlock Handle
9. Disconnect the Source Exchange Tool from the instrument (by rotation)
10. Replace the Vacuum Interlock Plug (by rotating)
11. Collapse the Vacuum Interlock Handle back to the starting position
12. Press the **Evacuate** button

13. Set temperature back to initial values (Transfer line temp 250 °C and Ion source temp 280 °C) and wait 30 minutes

14. Bakeout the orbitrap (4 hours)

NOTE: Bakeout system or let the source heat up for at least 3 hours (ideally overnight) to remove potential moisture absorbed on the source

To clean GC Q - Exactive EI Ion Source

1. Use aluminum oxide abrasive powder, methanol and cotton tipped applicator (moisten the cotton tipped applicator in methanol and then soak the aluminium powder) or sand paper for source cleaning or abrasive pencil for mechanical cleaning metal parts (Ion Cartridge Sleeve, Lens 3/RF Lens, Lens 2, Lens 1, Ion Volume, Repeller, Ion Volume - Repeller Insulator). It's not needed to clean with abrasive powder: Ion Volume - Repeller Insulator, Repeller Nut, Repeller Spring, Ion Volume Locking Ring)
2. Clean with a teethbrush under running water to remove all remaining aluminum powder
3. Rinse with Milli - Q water, then place in a beaker with Milli - Q water and sonicate for 5 minutes
4. Use tweezers to place components to new beaker, rinse with methanol, then place to beaker with fresh methanol and sonicate for 5 minutes
5. Use tweezers to place components to new beaker, rinse with acetone, then place to beaker with fresh acetone and sonicate for 5 minutes
6. Use tweezers to place components to new beaker, rinse with dichloromethane, then place to beaker with fresh dichloromethane and sonicate for 5 minutes
7. Use tweezers to place components to new beaker, rinse with toluene, then place to beaker with fresh toluene and sonicate for 5 minutes
8. Use tweezers to place components to new beaker, rinse with hexane, then place to beaker with fresh hexane and sonicate for 5 minutes

NOTE: Use hexane as a final cleaning step

9. Transfer to new beaker (with tweezer) and dry (use GC oven)
 10. After cooling down, assembly Ion Source Cartridge using Removing Ion Source
- The whole procedure is recorded on video "Cartridge Assembly".

Figure 4. Components of the GC Q - Exactive EI Ion Source Cartridge

To reassemble the ion source cartridge, continue in this order:

Figure 5. Inserting the Sleeve into the Source Holder

Figure 6. Inserting Lens 3/RF Lens into the Source Sleeve

Figure 7. Inserting Lens 2 into the Source Sleeve

Figure 8. Inserting Lens 1 into the Source Sleeve

Figure 9. Inserting the Ion Volume into the Source Sleeve

Figure 10. Inserting the Repeller

Figure 11. Inserting the Repeller Spring into the Sleeve

Figure 12. Inserting the Locking Ring into the Sleeve

NOTE: After contamination of the source with biological samples use dichloromethane (as described before) but do not use on plastic/ceramic parts

NOTE: After contamination of the source with siloxans ("column bleeding") use include also toluene

NOTE: Check the Repeller Spring, if it has a deformed shape and does not spring well there is a risk of reduced signal intensity. This part needs to be replaced after a certain period.